

STUDIES ON PHOTOCHEMICAL REACTIONS BETWEEN AMMONIUM MOLYBDATE AND VARIOUS ORGANIC REDUCING AGENTS IN WAVE-LENGTH 366 μ .

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The reduction of ammonium molybdate by tartaric acid, mandelic acid and lactic acid in ultraviolet light of 366 μ has been studied. The products of photoreduction vary in their physicochemical properties. Depending on the relative concentrations of the molybdate and the reductant, the reaction products are sometimes green, sometimes greenish yellow, sometimes pale yellow and even colourless. The green product predominates in excess concentration of molybdate and the colourless product predominates in excess concentration of the reductant. The kinetics of the reaction vary when the end-products of reaction are different. It has been found that the maximum velocity of reaction is obtained when the end-product is pale yellow in colour, the velocity of transformation being always less when the green products are formed.

Ghosh and his collaborators (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 14, 495) have made quantitative investigations on the oxidation of various reducing agents by photoactive sols of tungstic acid, molybdic acid, uranic acid, vanadic acid and ceric borate in both polarised and unpolarised lights. The results obtained may be grouped into two heads :—(i) with tungstic, vanadic and ceric borate sols, *l*-circularly polarised light has been found to be more effective than *d*-circularly polarised light in bringing out the photochemical reaction ; (ii) with molybdic and uranic acid sols, *d*- and *l*-circularly polarised lights have been found to have the same efficiency.

Hakomori (*Sci. Rep. Tohoku*, 1927, 18, 841) has shown that hexavalent uranium salt in neutral solution forms a complex with tartaric acid in molecular proportions and this complex undergoes photochemical reduction to the quadrivalent state on exposure to sunlight. Dumansky and Diatschkovsky (*J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 60, 1053) have shown that sodium tungstate forms a colloidal complex with tartaric acid solution which becomes blue on exposure to light. Gernez (*Compt. rend.*, 1887, 104, 785; 105, 85; 1889, 108, 942) investigated the changes in rotatory power of solutions of tartaric acid in presence of alkali molybdates with increasing concentration. He found maximum rotations when the acid and salts were mixed in equimolar proportion and this fact was considered to point to the formation of definite complex salts. The same method was adopted by Rosenheim and Itzig (*Ber.*, 1900, 33, 707) with tartaric acid and alkali molybdates and polymolybdates and also with tungstates and polytungstates. Klason and Kohler (*Ber.*, 1901, 34, 3946) extended Itzig's work and found that the maximum rotations given by sodium hydrogen tartrate depend on other factors beside the amount of alkali metal, such as the ratio of molybdic acid, concentration of the active substance and the temperature of the solution. Compounds of the general formula $R_2(XO)_3 \cdot C_4H_4O_6$ (R =alkali metal; X =Mo, W) have been prepared by Rosenheim and Itzig in the crystalline form. That complex formation occurs when ammonium molybdate is mixed with weak organic acids, viz., tartaric acid, lactic acid and mandelic acid, is supported by Britton and Jackson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1055).

The object of the present investigation was to study in details, the photoreduction of the complexes formed of ammonium molybdate and the various organic reducing acids, e.g., tartaric acid, mandelic acid and lactic acid in both polarised and unpolarised light.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The experimental arrangement was the same as was described by Ghosh and Bhattacharyya in a previous paper (*this issue*, p. 503) with one alteration. The spectral region of 366 μ was isolated with the help of "Schott and Gen ultraviolet filter no. 312".

Reagents.—Merck's extra pure ammonium molybdate, and *d*-tartaric acid, *l*-tartaric acid and racemic acid supplied by "Dr. Landau and Frankel Co." further purified by crystallisation; Kahlbaum's extra pure *l*-lactic acid and *r*-mandelic acid were used throughout the investigation. For making solutions bi-distilled water was used. For pH control Merck's extra pure HCl was used.

Measurement of the Velocity of Reaction.—The velocity of reaction was determined by pipetting out 0.98 c.c. of the reaction mixture in a conical flask containing 5 c.c. of dilute H_2SO_4 (1:20) and titrating the reduced molybdate with 0.0115N- $KMnO_4$ solution by means of a microburette. It is to be pointed out here that $KMnO_4$ solution of the above concentration cannot oxidise tartaric acid, lactic acid or mandelic acid in the cold; so that the reduced molybdate was easily estimated by means of 0.0115N- $KMnO_4$ in presence of the above reducing acids. The reactions were carried out at 29°. The p_H value of the mixture was measured electrometrically by using a quinhydrone electrode.

The reduction of ammonium molybdate by tartaric acid, lactic acid and mandelic acid does not proceed in the dark but on exposure to light of radiation 366 μ rapid reaction goes on.

The products of photoreduction vary in their properties. Depending on the relative concentrations of the molybdate and the reductant, the reaction products are sometimes green, sometimes greenish yellow, sometimes pale yellow and even colourless. The green product predominates in excess of molybdate, and the colourless product predominates in excess of the reductant. The kinetics of photochemical reactions will naturally vary when the end-products of reaction are different. We have found that the maximum velocity of photochemical reaction is obtained when the end-product is pale yellow in colour, the velocity of transformation being always less when the green products are formed.

Intensity Measurement.—The intensity of radiation absorbed by the reaction mixture was measured by means of a Moll galvanometer and a Moll thermopile calibrated by means of a standard lamp, supplied by the Bureau of Standards. The intensity of absorbed radiation was measured by noting the deflections when the light passed through (a) pure water alone and (b) the reaction mixture. The difference in deflections in the two cases gave the intensity of radiation absorbed by the reaction mixture.

The results are tabulated in Tables I to VIII. In the given tables $\Delta x/\Delta t$ =zero molecular velocity constant=changes in concentration of 0.98 c.c. of ammonium molybdate per minute in terms of c.c. of 0.0115N- $KMnO_4$.

TABLE I.

Effect of varying the concentrations of both ammonium molybdate and tartaric acid.

Reductant=d-tartaric acid. Temp. (θ)=29°. p_H =1.71. Wave-length (λ)=366 μ .

Conc. of Mo. ^a	Concentration of tartaric acid in normality.										
		0.025	0.05	0.075	0.1	0.125	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.8	
0.025N	$\Delta x/\Delta t.10^4$	20.0	30.8	30.2	20.4	13.7	...	10.8	...	...	
	Colour of the product	Green	Pale yellow	Colourless	Colourless	Colourless	...	Colourless	...	...	
	$I_{abs}.10^{-18}$	41.0	41.0	41.0	41.0	41.0	...	53.8	...	...	
0.05	$\Delta x/\Delta t.10^4$	...	30.0	30.0	30.3	...	20.1	20.0	...	...	
	Colour	...	Green	Greenish yellow	Pale yellow	...	Colourless	Colourless	...	...	
	$I_{abs}.10^{-18}$	...	42.8	44.0	44.2	...	50.0	53.8	...	...	
0.1	$\Delta x/\Delta t.10^4$	10.0	21.6	30.0	43.3	43.3	43.3	43.3	43.3	43.3	
	Colour	Green	Green	Green	Green	Greenish yellow	Pale yellow	Colourless	Colourless	Colourless	
	$I_{abs}.10^{-18}$	53.8	57.0	57.0	57.0	57.0	57.0	57.0	57.0	57.0	
0.2	$\Delta x/\Delta t.10^4$	5.5	9.09	16.6	21.6	27.0	43.0	86.6	86.6	86.6	
	Colour	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Pale yellow	Colourless	Colourless	
	$I_{abs}.10^{-18}$	54.4	54.4	54.4	54.4	54.4	55.6	55.6	55.6	55.6	

I_{abs} =no. of quanta absorbed per c.c. per second.

^a The equivalent weight of molybdate has been calculated on the basis of one equivalent containing one gram atom of molybdenum.

TABLE II.

Effect of varying the concentration of both ammonium molybdate and mandelic acid.

Reductant = *r*-Mandelic Acid. $\theta = 29^\circ$. $p_n = 1.71$. $\lambda = 366 \mu\mu$.

Conc. of Mo.		Conc. of mandelic acid in normality						
		0.025	0.05	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.4
0.025N	$\Delta x / \Delta t \cdot 10^4$	16.6	40.0	34.4	34.7	36.6	—	—
	Colour	Green	Pale yellow	Colourless	Colourless	Colourless	Colourless	—
0.05	$\Delta x / \Delta t \cdot 10^4$	65.4	65.4	65.4	69.2	69.8	—	—
	Colour	Green	Green	Greenish yellow	Pale yellow	Colourless	—	—
0.1	$\Delta x / \Delta t \cdot 10^4$	14.2	25.0	43.3	53.3	80.0	—	—
	Colour	Green	Green	Greenish yellow	Pale yellow	Colourless	—	—
0.2	$\Delta x / \Delta t \cdot 10^4$	65.4	76.2	76.2	76.2	76.2	—	—
	Colour	Green	Green	Green	Greenish yellow	Pale yellow	Colourless	—
0.4	$\Delta x / \Delta t \cdot 10^4$	10.4	21.7	40.0	80.0	120.0	123.3	—
	Colour	Green	Green	Green	Greenish yellow	Pale yellow	Colourless	—
0.8	$\Delta x / \Delta t \cdot 10^4$	72.0	72.0	72.0	72.0	72.0	72.0	—
	Colour	Green	Green	Green	Green	Greenish yellow	Pale yellow	—
1.6	$\Delta x / \Delta t \cdot 10^4$	8.8	16.6	33.0	67.0	120.0	123.3	—
	Colour	Green	Green	Green	Green	Greenish yellow	Pale yellow	—

TABLE III.

Effect of varying the conc. of *l*-lactic acid. $\theta = 29^\circ$. $p_n = 1.71$. $\lambda = 366 \mu\mu$. Conc. of Mo = 0.2 N.

	Conc. in normality of lactic acid.					
	0.15	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.6	0.8
$\Delta x / \Delta t \cdot 10^4$	14.1	25.0	37.0	53.3	65.2	63.1
Colour	Green	Green	Green	Greenish yellow	Pale yellow	Colourless
$I_{abs} \cdot 10^{-10}$	55.8	60.0	60.0	60.0	60.0	60.0

TABLE V.

Effect of varying the intensity of absorbed radiation.

 $\lambda = 366 \mu\mu$. $\theta = 29^\circ$. $p_n = 1.71$.

$I_{abs} \cdot 10^{-10}$.	Mo.	Reductant.	$\Delta x / \Delta t \cdot 10^4$	$(\Delta x / \Delta t)_n$	$(\Delta x / \Delta t)_n$	$[I_{abs}]_n$
<i>d</i> -Tartaric acid.						
I	57.0	0.1N	0.2N	43.3	4.6	5.7
II	10.0	0.1	0.1	9.3		
<i>r</i> -Mandelic acid.						
I	74.0	0.2	0.2	67.0	3.9	3.9
II	19.2	0.2	0.2	17.1		
<i>l</i> -Lactic acid.						
I	60.0	0.2	0.2	25.0	4.9	5.2
II	11.6	0.2	0.2	5.2		

TABLE VII.

Effect of varying the p_n . $\theta = 29^\circ$. $\lambda = 366 \mu\mu$. Conc. of Mo = 0.2 N.

$I_{abs} \cdot 10^{-10}$.	p_n .	[Tartaric acid].	$\Delta x / \Delta t \cdot 10^4$.
54.4	4.95	0.025N	4.6
54.4	1.71	"	5.5
54.4	4.09	0.075	12.1
54.4	1.71	"	16.6

TABLE IV.

Effect of varying the conc. of ammonium molybdate.

 $\theta = 29^\circ$. $p_n = 1.71$. $\lambda = 366 \mu\mu$. Lactic acid = 0.4 N.

	Conc. of Mo. in normality.					
	0.0125	0.025	0.05	0.1	0.2	0.4
$\Delta x / \Delta t \cdot 10^4$	7.0	14.7	26.3	53.1	53.3	—
Colour	Colourless	Colourless	Colourless	Colourless	Colourless	Greenish yellow
$I_{abs} \cdot 10^{-10}$	52.0	56.0	56.0	60.0	60.0	—

TABLE VI.

Effect of varying the nature of tartaric acid.

 $I_{abs} \times 10^{-10} = 57.0$. λ , and p_n as in Table V.

	Conc. of Mo.	Conc. of Reductant.	$\Delta x / \Delta t \cdot 10^4$.
<i>d</i> -Tartaric acid.	0.1N	0.1N	43.3
<i>l</i> -Tartaric acid.	"	"	"
Racemic acid.	"	"	"

TABLE VIII.

Quantum efficiency of the process.

 $\lambda = 366 \mu\mu$. $\theta = 29^\circ$. $p_n = 1.71$. $n =$ No. of molecules transformed per c.c. per second.

Conc. of Mo.	Conc. of reductant.	$n \cdot 10^{-10}$	$I_{abs} \cdot 10^{-10}$.	η .
<i>d</i> -Tartaric acid.				
0.2N	0.2N	50.9	55.6	0.9
0.1	0.1	51.3	57.0	0.9
0.2	0.4	102.7	55.6	1.8
<i>r</i> -Mandelic acid.				
0.2	0.2	20.2	19.2	1.1
0.1	0.1	47.4	72.4	0.7
0.2	0.3	142.2	74.3	1.9
<i>l</i> -Lactic acid.				
0.2	0.2	29.6	59.9	0.5
0.2	0.6	77.2	61.0	1.3

Thus we see that the velocity constant increases slightly with decrease in p_n .

From Table V, we see that the velocity of reaction is directly proportional to the intensity of absorbed radiation. From Table VI we see that different optical isomeric tartaric acids as well as racemic acid have got the same efficiency in the photoreduction of ammonium molybdate. Table VIII shows that quantum efficiency is nearly unity.

It was found that unpolarised, plane polarised, *d*- and *l*- circularly polarised lights are equally effective in bringing out photoreduction of ammonium molybdate by *d*-tartaric acid, *l*-tartaric acid, racemic acid, *l*-lactic acid and τ -mandelic acid.

D I S C U S S I O N.

Table I.—(a) With excess of tartaric acid, the products are always colourless and the whole of the incident radiation is absorbed. In the vertical column corresponding to 0.4*N* tartaric acid, it will be seen that the velocity of reaction increases as the concentration of molybdate increases; the proportionality is nearly exact.

(b) For relatively low concentration of tartaric acid, when the reaction product is definitely green, horizontal columns 3 and 4 show that for a fixed concentration of molybdate the velocity of reaction is also proportional to the concentration of tartaric acid. Again comparison of the data in horizontal column 3 with the corresponding data in horizontal column 4 show that for the same amount of light absorption, the velocity is inversely as the concentration of molybdate.

(c) The velocity of reaction for any one concentration of molybdate becomes maximum when the relative concentration of molybdate and tartrate are such that the reaction product looks pale yellow in colour. In this region the reaction mixture consists approximately of two equivalents of tartaric acid to one equivalent of molybdate, the equivalent weight of molybdate being calculated on the basis of one equivalent containing one gram atom of molybdenum.

Table II.—The results with mandelic acid as reductant are generally similar to those obtained with tartaric acid as reductant. Thus, for excess concentration of mandelic acid, 0.3*N*, when the reaction products are colourless $[Mo] = 0.025N, 0.05N$, the velocity of reaction is approximately proportional to the concentration of molybdate. Again, as will be seen from horizontal columns 2, 3 and 4, when the reaction products are definitely green-coloured, for any one concentration of molybdate, the velocity of reaction is proportional to the concentration of mandelic acid. In this region also the reaction velocity for any one concentration of mandelic acid diminishes as the concentration of molybdate increases. The pale yellow solutions, which are obtained by reduction, in the region of concentration 1 Mo:2 mandelic acid (approximately), are characterised by the maximum velocity of reaction.

Tables III and IV.—The experimental data on the velocity of photoreduction of molybdate by lactic acid are similar in general features to those observed with tartaric acid or mandelic acid as reductant.

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